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“PEOPLE ARE STRESSED AND BURNED OUT”

People work here and there
People move here and there
Deadlines, Briefings, Meetings
Traffic, Rush, and Panic
People are stressed here and there

At the end of the day
People are burned out here and there
People are stressed and tired
Exhausted, and Frustrated
Work seems to have no end

People should rest and stop
Avoid being stressed and burned out
Or their body will stop
Be slow, rest, and sleep
Happiness, people will meet